

1 A cohesive zone model for fatigue under cyclic thermo-hydro-mechanical loading

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3 Abstract

4 Rocks can undergo fatigue failure when subjected to cyclic mechanical, hydraulic, or thermal loadings, or a
5 combination of these. Therefore, accounting for possible fatigue damage is important for subsurface engineering
6 projects, such as the cyclic stimulation of geothermal reservoirs. However, existing models do not simultaneously
7 account for degradation of both tensile strength and stiffness under varying-amplitude loading and coupled
8 thermo-hydro-mechanical (THM) conditions. To address this, a new cohesive zone model is developed to
9 account for the effect of fatigue on tensile strength and stiffness. The model is then used within the framework
10 of zero-thickness interface elements to simulate the response of pre-existing or new fractures. Hydraulic and
11 thermal processes are included in both the cohesive interface elements and the continuum elements, allowing the
12 consideration of coupled thermo-hydro-mechanical processes. The fatigue damage variable is set to evolve with
13 the number and magnitude of cycles according to Palmgren-Miner's rule. The proposed method is validated
14 against three laboratory tests from the literature, including cyclic Brazilian test, cyclic hydraulic fracturing
15 test and cyclic thermal stimulation test. All three validation results show that the fatigue damage or reduced
16 breakdown pressure can be well reproduced. Mesh sensitivity based on the simulation of the Brazilian test, in
17 which interface elements are inserted in-between all the continuum elements, highlights the influence of the mesh
18 orientation and mesh density on the simulation results. In addition, stabilisation of the method is demonstrated
19 by increasing the mechanical viscosity, which must be used with care to avoid predicting a longer fatigue life.
20 The ability of the method to handle varying-amplitude cyclic loading is demonstrated by the simulation of a
21 synthetic cyclic loading scheme based on the Brazilian test. The proposed method can be used to support the
22 design of cyclic thermal stimulation campaigns for geothermal (or other) reservoirs, by being able to simulate
23 the reduction in strength due to fatigue, and thus reducing stimulation pressures needed.

24 *Keywords:* Fracturing, Thermo-hydro-mechanics, Geothermal energy, Cohesive zone model

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25 1. Introduction

26 Rock fatigue failure is a common phenomenon in subsurface engineering projects, and can be either beneficial
27 (e.g., fatigue cracks near geothermal or hydrocarbon wells (Hofmann et al., 2021; Zang et al., 2025)) or detri-
28 mental (e.g., fatigue damage of dams (Meng et al., 2023)). The fatigue damage of rocks subjected to cyclic
29 mechanical, hydraulic or thermal loading has been extensively studied, demonstrating that rock strength can
30 be reduced and that fracture patterns can become more complex under cyclic loading (Cerfontaine and Collin,
31 2018; Zang et al., 2021; Jung et al., 2021; Niu et al., 2023). For example, cyclic Brazilian tests conducted by
32 Erarslan and Williams (2012) and Liu et al. (2018) have shown that rock samples fail under lower ultimate
33 loads and exhibit different fracturing mechanism compared to those under monotonic loading.

34 In addition to pure mechanical loading, coupled hydro-mechanical and thermo-mechanical loadings have also
35 been used to induce fatigue damage in rocks. Laboratory cyclic hydraulic fracturing tests on sandstone and
36 granite samples have shown significant reductions in breakdown pressure (up to 20% for Pocheon granite cores
37 (Zhuang et al., 2019), 7.18% - 18.9% for Xujiahe sandstone (Kang et al., 2020), and 16% for dry Tennessee
38 sandstone) (Patel et al., 2017). Laboratory tests have also shown that cyclic hydraulic stimulation can lead
39 to the formation of more complex fracture networks, as opposed to the simpler fractures typically induced
40 by conventional hydraulic stimulation (Patel et al., 2017; Wei et al., 2023). Moreover, the effectiveness of
41 cyclic hydraulic fracturing has been demonstrated in field-scale tests, such as the cyclic hydraulic stimulation
42 of well PX-1 at the Pohang enhanced geothermal system (EGS) project site, South Korea, which demonstrated
43 that cyclic injection was able to improve well performance while ensuring that seismic activity remains below
44 the target threshold of M_w 2.0 (Hofmann et al., 2019; Zang et al., 2021). In addition, cyclic heating-cooling
45 treatment on rocks can also reduce their strength, which has been demonstrated in experiments (Gasc-Barbier
46 et al., 2014; Zhu et al., 2020). However, study of rock fatigue damage under cyclic fully coupled thermo-hydro-
47 mechanical (THM) loadings is rarely reported. Cyclic THM processes can happen during, for example, soft
48 stimulation of geothermal reservoirs. A combination of thermal stress and fatigue damage may further accelerate
49 the rock failures. Therefore, the investigation of the rock fatigue damage under cyclic THM loadings is necessary
50 and meaningful, while existing literature mainly focuses on individual loadings and simple hydro-mechanical or
51 thermo-mechanical loadings.

52 Numerical simulation provides an essential tool for understanding fatigue damage of rocks. Incorporating
53 fatigue damage into the cohesive zone model is a common method to predict the onset and propagation of
54 fatigue fractures. The cohesive zone model was first proposed by Dugdale (1960) and Barenblatt (1962) to
55 circumvent the unrealistic infinite stresses at the fracture tip obtained for a linear elastic material, assuming
56 a cohesive-law governed zone in front of the fracture tip. Later, Hillerborg et al. (1976) introduced CZM into
57 FEM to simulate crack initiation and growth in concrete. When discretising the material domain, the material
58 separation and thus damage of the structure can be described by interface elements in-between continuum
59 elements (Scheider, 2001), governed by the cohesive law that relates traction and separation of the two surfaces
60 of the interface element. It has the advantages of being capable of simulating fracture initiation, an intuitive
61 physical meaning and its mitigation of the need to calculate the stress singularity at the fracture tip over other
62 approaches like extended finite element method. The traction-separation law, consisting of elastic and softening
63 curves, is controlled by two material parameters, i.e. the critical fracture energy G_I (for mode-I fracture) and
64 the tensile strength σ_{n0} , shown in Fig.2a. The damage of the rock, after the tensile strength is reached, is

65 described by the softening curve.

66 Traditionally, the law can only describe damage due to monotonic loading beyond a strength threshold, i.e.

67 if loading remains below the strength, the behaviour is elastic, with no additional damage, regardless of the

68 number of loading cycles. Previous efforts have been made to incorporate fatigue damage due to cyclic loading

69 into cohesive laws (Roe and Siegmund, 2003; Maiti and Geubelle, 2005; Robinson et al., 2005; Turon et al., 2007;

70 Khoramishad et al., 2010; De Moura and Gonçalves, 2015; Choi et al., 2020; Xi et al., 2021; Wei et al., 2023).

71 For example, Robinson et al. (2005) incorporated a fatigue damage variable into the cohesive law based on a

72 modified Paris power law equation, which relates the fatigue crack growth rate (da/dN , a is the fatigue crack

73 length and N the number of cycles) to the amplitude of the applied stress intensity factor ($\Delta K = K_{\max} - K_{\min}$,

74 K_{\max} is the maximum stress intensity factor while K_{\min} the minimum). The model was used to simulate

75 delamination growth in composite material and their numerical results showed that the model can reproduce

76 the characteristics of the Paris power law that is commonly observed in experiments, though the model considers

77 only the maximum load. Munoz et al. (2006) further extended the work of Robinson et al. (2005) to consider

78 the cyclic loads with non-zero minimum value. Turon et al. (2007) developed a cohesive zone model with

79 a single damage variable and related the damage state with the number of cycles and the loading conditions.

80 Khoramishad et al. (2010) integrated a strain-based fatigue damage with the cohesive law to simulate the impact

81 of cyclic loading on the bonded joints. Unlike most of the previous models, the degradation of the cohesive

82 strength is possible and dependent on the fatigue damage, making it possible to accumulate fatigue damage

83 before the cohesive separation stage is reached. Xi et al. (2021) and Wei et al. (2023) followed this concept but

84 formulated the fatigue damage variable as a function of the number of cycles. One limitation in those models

85 is that the cohesive stiffness remains unchanged in the elastic stage. In contrast, some other literatures, e.g.

86 Nojavan et al. (2016a); Choi et al. (2020), presented the computation of the damage evolution during cyclic

87 loading is in conjunction with an unloading–reloading relation in the cohesive zone model, while allowing the

88 degradation of the reloading stiffness.

89 While existing models have advantages and limitations in incorporating and computing fatigue damage, none

90 address fully coupled thermo-hydro-mechanical loading, which requires the consideration of the thermal pro-

91 cesses in the cohesive interface element. In addition, a specific cracking path was prescribed along a pre-defined

92 line in most of the modelling exercises in the previously mentioned literature, while the cases where fracture can

93 initiate and propagate in the most efficient fracturing paths are not considered. These limitations render the

94 models unsuitable for simulating fatigue failure in, e.g. geothermal reservoirs, where fractures can propagate in

95 arbitrary but most efficient direction. In addition, the re-loading stiffness is unchanged if the traction-separation

96 path is in the elastic stage in previous models (Khoramishad et al., 2010; Xi et al., 2021; Wei et al., 2023), which

97 fails to capture the observed degradation of rock stiffness and the accumulation of deformation (Cerfontaine

98 and Collin, 2018; Xiao et al., 2010). Wei et al. (2023) also formulated the fatigue damage variable as a function

99 of the number of cycles under constant-amplitude loading, which does not consider varying-amplitude cyclic

100 loading.

101 In this paper, we introduce a fatigue damage variable into the cohesive zone model, which, together with co-

102 hesive interface elements and continuum elements that consider fully coupled THM processes, can simulate

103 fatigue failures under cyclic THM loading. While the principles of the formulation can apply to mixed mode

104 (shear and tension) damage, we consider tensile fatigue for clarity and due to the stress path in near well-bore

105 conditions where thermo-hydraulic stimulation may be considered. The fatigue damage variable is calibrated

106 using the number of loading cycles and fatigue life at different load intensities (S-N curve, or stress-number
107 of cycles curve). With this formulation, the tensile strength and stiffness of the interface element both de-
108 grade with increasing number of cycles. Palmgren-Miner’s rule is used to account for varying-amplitude cyclic
109 loading. While the traction-separation law is temperature-invariant, the thermal expansion and contraction of
110 the continuum elements lead to stress changes, which can generate cyclic stresses under varying temperature
111 cycles, and therefore includes the impact of thermally-induced stresses. The proposed method is validated
112 against three laboratory tests from the literature, including cyclic Brazilian test, cyclic hydraulic fracturing
113 test and cyclic thermal stimulation test to demonstrate its ability to capture fatigue damage under cyclic cou-
114 pled THM processes, including varying amplitude loading. The proposed model can be used to simulate cyclic
115 thermo-hydraulic stimulation in subsurface projects, e.g. geothermal projects, and rock failures in subsurface
116 infrastructure projects, e.g. the damaged zone under cyclic THM loading around radioactive waste repositories.

117 2. Method

118 2.1. Modelling approach

119 Continuum finite elements are employed to represent intact rock, whereas zero-thickness three-node interface
120 elements are used to model discontinuities (Fig. 1). The interface elements can be inserted between continuum
121 elements along a pre-defined path to model pre-existing fractures or weak planes, or can be placed between
122 all continuum elements to enable arbitrary cracking paths. The interface element has a total of 9 nodes,
123 equally distributed on top, mid, and bottom planes. The bottom and top faces of the interface element share
124 nodes with the continuum elements, each having four degrees of freedom at each node, corresponding to the
125 x and y coordinates, water pressure p_w , and temperature T . The mid-plane nodes have only two degrees of
126 freedom for water pressure p_w and temperature T . In this way, different constitutive laws can be used for the
127 continuum and the discontinuities, allowing for a more flexible representation of heat and fluid flows along and
128 across the fracture (Luo et al., 2025). Therefore, such interface elements can be used for applications where an
129 explicit representation of the mid-plane pressure and temperature is convenient, such as the interfaces between
130 permeable and impermeable materials.

Fig. 1: Finite elements used. (a) Interface elements between continuum elements to represent pre-existing or potential cracking paths. (b) Node numbering, nodal degrees of freedom and local basis for the interface element (Luo et al., 2025).

131 *2.2. Governing equations for the continuum porous medium*

132 The governing equations for the continuum elements follow the formulation proposed by Collin et al. (2002).
 133 The theoretical framework is composed of three balance equations, namely the water mass balance equation,
 134 the balance of momentum (or stress equilibrium) equation, and the energy balance equation. These equations,
 135 together with the necessary constitutive laws, are presented below.

136 *2.2.1. Hydraulic problem*

137 The water mass balance equation reads:

$$\frac{\partial(\phi\rho_w)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_w \mathbf{v}_w) = 0 \quad (1)$$

138 where ϕ is the porosity, ρ_w [kg/m³] is the water density, t [s] is time, and \mathbf{v}_w [m/s] the Darcy velocity vector.
 139 The water density is a function of both water pressure p_w [Pa] and temperature T [K] according to:

$$\rho_w = \rho_{w0} \left[1 + \frac{p_w - p_{w0}}{\kappa_w} - \beta_w (T - T_0) \right] \quad (2)$$

140 where ρ_{w0} is the water density at the reference pressure p_{w0} and reference temperature T_0 , κ [1/Pa] is the water
 141 compressibility, and β_w [1/K] is the thermal expansion coefficient.

142 The Darcy velocity vector is defined as:

$$\mathbf{v}_w = -\frac{K}{\mu_w} \nabla p_w \quad (3)$$

143 where K [m²] is the intrinsic permeability, and μ_w [Pa · s] is the water dynamic viscosity, which is a function
 144 of temperature according to (Ewen and Thomas, 1989):

$$\mu_w = 0.6612(T - 229)^{-1.562} \quad (4)$$

145 *2.2.2. Mechanical problem*

146 If equilibrium state is assumed and if gravity is neglected, the balance of momentum reads:

$$\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{0} \quad (5)$$

147 where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ [Pa] is the Cauchy's total stress tensor.

148 The behaviour of the intact rock is assumed to follow a linear elastic law. Assuming that compressive stress
 149 and strain are defined as negative, the thermo-poro-elastic constitutive law reads:

$$\Delta \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbb{C} : \Delta \boldsymbol{\epsilon} - \Delta p_w \mathbf{I} - \beta_b K_b \Delta T \mathbf{I} \quad (6)$$

150 where \mathbb{C} is the 4th-order elastic stiffness tensor, $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ is the strain tensor, \mathbf{I} is the 2nd-order identity tensor, β_b is
 151 the bulk volumetric thermal expansion coefficient, and K_b [Pa] is the drained bulk modulus.

152 *2.2.3. Thermal problem*

153 Under the assumption of local thermal equilibrium, with no internal source or sink, the energy balance equation
 154 reads:

$$\frac{\partial [(\rho c_p)_b T]}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q}_T = 0 \quad (7)$$

155 where $(\rho c_p)_b$ is the bulk volumetric heat capacity and \mathbf{q}_T [J/(m² · s)] is the heat flux vector. The bulk volumetric
 156 heat capacity is given by:

$$(\rho c_p)_b = (1 - \phi) (\rho_s c_{ps}) + \phi (\rho_w c_{pw}) \quad (8)$$

157 where c_p [J/(kg · K)] is the phase specific heat capacity, ρ is the phase density, and the subscripts s and w refer
 158 to the solid and water phases, respectively.

159 The heat flux vector is given by:

$$\mathbf{q}_T = -\lambda_b \nabla T + \rho_w c_{pw} \mathbf{q}_D T \quad (9)$$

160 where the first term corresponds to Fourier's law and the second term corresponds to heat advection due to
 161 water flow. λ_b [J/(m · s · K)] is the bulk thermal conductivity, given by:

$$\lambda_b = (1 - \phi) \lambda_s + \phi \lambda_w \quad (10)$$

162 where λ_s and λ_w are the thermal conductivities of the solid and water phases, respectively.

163 2.3. Governing equations for the discontinuities

164 The mechanical and hydraulic governing equations for the interface elements are inherited from Luo et al. (2025)
 165 with the gas phase being neglected. Additionally, the governing equations for thermal processes are included
 166 here. Note that the following equations are tailored for 2D problems.

167 2.3.1. Hydraulic problem

168 The mass balance for water in a differential volume of discontinuity $w dl$ reads:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(w \rho_w) + \frac{\partial q_w^l}{\partial l} - q_w^b - q_w^t = 0 \quad (11)$$

169 where w [m] is the width of the discontinuity, q_w^l [kg/(m · s)] is the longitudinal water mass flux, and q_w^b and
 170 q_w^t [kg/(m² · s)] are the transversal water mass fluxes incoming to the discontinuity from surrounding continuum
 171 medium.

172 The mass fluxes in Eq. (11) can be expanded as:

$$q_w^l = \rho_w v_w^l; \quad q_w^b = \rho_w v_w^b; \quad q_w^t = \rho_w v_w^t \quad (12)$$

173 where v_w^l [m²/s], v_w^b [m/s] and v_w^t [m/s] are the longitudinal and transversal (top and bottom) volumetric fluxes.
 174 These fluxes are obtained from the following generalised Darcy's law:

$$v_w^l = -\frac{t^l}{\mu_w} \frac{\partial p_w^m}{\partial l}; \quad v_w^b = -\frac{k^b}{\mu_w} \check{p}_w^b; \quad v_w^t = -\frac{k^t}{\mu_w} \check{p}_w^t \quad (13)$$

175 where t^l [m³] is the longitudinal hydraulic coefficient, k^b [m²] and k^t [m²] are the transversal permeability of
 176 the interface, p_w^m [Pa] is the water pressure at the middle plane, defined as positive if larger than atmospheric
 177 pressure (101.325 kPa). \check{p}_w^b [Pa] and \check{p}_w^t [Pa] are the transversal pressure jumps between the bottom and top
 178 faces and the mid-plane, respectively. The transversal pressure drops are defined as follows:

$$\check{p}_w^b = (p_w^m - p_w^b); \quad \check{p}_w^t = (p_w^m - p_w^t) \quad (14)$$

179 where p_w^b and p_w^t are the water pressures at the bottom and top sides of the discontinuity.

180 The longitudinal hydraulic coefficient t^l is estimated using the Reynolds lubrication equation, which describes
 181 the laminar flow of an incompressible and Newtonian fluid flowing between two parallel plates (Zimmerman and
 182 Yeo, 2000). It reads:

$$t^l = \frac{r_n^3}{12} + t_0^l \quad (15)$$

183 where r_n [m] is the normal separation of the interface, and t_0^l [m³] is the initial longitudinal hydraulic coefficient,
 184 which makes it possible to assign an initial longitudinal transmissivity to the discontinuity even if it is closed
 185 from the mechanical point of view. The longitudinal hydraulic coefficient t^l , defined in Eq. (11), plays a similar
 186 role as the intrinsic permeability K in the equation governing fluid flow in the continuum. Both parameters
 187 account only for the geometrical characteristics of the medium through which the liquid flows, i.e., they are
 188 independent of the fluid properties. The fluid properties (as well as the time dimension) are introduced via the
 189 water dynamic viscosity μ_w in Eqs. (2) and (9), for the continuum and discontinuities, respectively.
 190 The width w will evolve with the normal separation of interface r_n :

$$w = r_n + w_0 \quad (16)$$

191 where w_0 [m] can be set to be non-zero to assign an initial storage volume to the discontinuity even if it is
 192 mechanically closed (Liaudat et al., 2023).

193 2.3.2. Mechanical problem

194 The balance of momentum for the interface element reads:

$$\frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}_c}{\partial l} = \mathbf{0} \quad (17)$$

195 where l is the longitudinal axis of the interface element, and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_c = [\sigma_n, \sigma_l]$ [Pa] is the total stress on the interface
 196 mid-plane, with σ_n and σ_l being the normal and shear stress components on that plane. This paper focuses on
 197 mode I fracturing. The shear stress component is therefore not discussed here.

198 For the mechanical constitutive behaviour of the discontinuity, the bilinear traction-separation law schematically
 199 depicted in Fig. 2 is used (Mi et al., 1998; Liaudat et al., 2023). More advanced constitutive laws can be
 200 incorporated easily into the code. This bilinear law can describe the behaviour of fractures using six parameters:
 201 the maximum tension and shear strengths, σ_{n0} [Pa] and σ_{l0} [Pa], the normal and shear "cracking" separation,
 202 r_{n0} [m] and r_{l0} [m], and the normal and shear debonding separations, r_{nc} [m] and r_{lc} [m].

Fig. 2: The elasto-damage law. (a) Tensile branch incorporating the fatigue damage; (b) Shear branch

203 Upon loading, the normal and shear stresses are given by:

$$\sigma'_n = \begin{cases} (1 - D) K_{nm} r_n & \text{if } r_n \geq 0 \\ K_{n0} r_n & \text{if } r_n \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

$$\sigma_1 = (1 - D) K_{10} r_1 \quad (19)$$

where σ'_n [Pa] represents Terzaghi's effective normal stress, defined as $\sigma'_n = \sigma_n + p_w^m$, and $K_{n0} = \sigma_{n0}/r_{n0}$ [Pa/m] is the initial normal slope $K_{nm} = \sigma_{nm}/r_{n0}$ is the normal stiffness after m th cycles and $\sigma_{nm} = (1 - D_f)\sigma_{n0}$. D_f is the fatigue damage variable and will be defined later. σ_1 and r_1 are the tangential stress and separation respectively, and $K_{10} = \sigma_{10}/r_{10}$ is the tangential slope. (Note that the friction is not included in the shear branch.) When an interface element is used to represent natural fractures, the normal slope can have a physical meaning, interpreted as fracture stiffness, for instance, as a result of interpenetration of fracture surfaces due to presence of asperities (Cerfontaine et al., 2015; Lei and Barton, 2022). In the context of this paper, K_{n0} is interpreted as penalty coefficients, thus allowing negligible interpenetration of fracture surfaces regardless of their roughness (Cerfontaine et al., 2015). To enforce the contact constraints, the slope should be set high enough to reduce artificial compliance (Liaudat et al., 2023). However, the choice of their values is a trade-off between having artificial compliance and having numerical convergence problems. Additionally, D is the damage variable ranging from 0 (intact rock) to 1 (fully separated fracture). This damage variable evolves as follows:

$$D = \min\left(\frac{\bar{\omega}}{1 + \bar{\omega}} \frac{1}{\eta}, 1\right) \quad (20)$$

$$\bar{\omega} = \max(\omega) \quad (21)$$

$$\omega = \left\langle \left(\frac{\langle r_n \rangle}{r_{n0}} \right)^\beta + \left(\frac{|r_1|}{r_{10}} \right)^{1/\beta} - 1 \right\rangle \quad (22)$$

$$\eta = 1 - \frac{r_{n0}}{r_{nc}} = 1 - \frac{r_{10}}{r_{1c}} \quad (23)$$

where ω is a positive scalar that defines the mechanical degradation of the interface element for a given normal separations, $\bar{\omega}$ is a history variable that stores the maximum value reached by ω during the loading history, and $\langle \cdot \rangle = (\cdot + |\cdot|)/2$ is the Macaulay bracket (Liaudat et al., 2023). β is a material parameter that characterise the mixed mode damage and is assumed to be 1 in this work (Liaudat et al., 2023). The above equations state that if the separation r_n is less than the normal crack separation r_{n0} , the damage variable D is then zero. If $r_{n0} < r_n < r_{nc}$, D is between 0 and 1, determined by the ratio of $(r_n - r_{n0})/(r_{nc} - r_{n0})$. Otherwise if r_n is beyond the debonding separation r_{nc} , D is forced to be 1, indicating a completely separation of the interface element.

To determine the fatigue damage variable, a linear strength degradation is assumed (Xi et al., 2021; Nojavan et al., 2016b). Thus, when subjected to constant-amplitude cyclic loading (Fig. 3a), it is defined as:

$$D_f = \left(1 - \frac{\sigma'_A}{\sigma_{n0}}\right) \frac{m}{M_f} \quad (24)$$

where σ'_A [Pa] is the amplitude of the cyclic loading (effective stress). M_f is the fatigue life (maximum number of cycles until failure) under a specific constant-amplitude cyclic loading.

When subjected to varying-amplitude cyclic loading shown in (Fig. 3b), Equation 24 can be further developed based on the Palmgren-Miner's rule, which reads:

$$D_f = \sum_i \left(1 - \frac{\sigma'_{Ai}}{\sigma_{n0}}\right) \frac{1}{M_{fi}} \quad (25)$$

230 where i indicates the i th cyclic loading that has a maximum amplitude of σ'_{Ai} , as shown in Fig. 3b. M_{fi} is the
 231 fatigue life corresponding to the applied loading level σ'_{Ai} .

232 An empirical S-N relationship is used as a criterion to determine the fatigue life M_{fi} , which relates the maximum
 233 value of the cyclic loading (σ'_{Ai}) to the fatigue life M_{fi} of the rock. This relationship has been widely used in
 234 metals, concrete, and rocks (Nojavan et al., 2016b; Chen et al., 2017; Cerfontaine and Collin, 2018; Xi et al.,
 235 2021). It reads (Cerfontaine and Collin, 2018; Xi et al., 2021):

$$\frac{\sigma'_{Ai}}{\sigma_{n0}} = a \log_{10} M_{fi} + b \quad (26)$$

236 where a and b are model parameters that can be determined from experimental data.

Fig. 3: Different loading scenarios.

237 Moreover, mechanical viscosity is added to the contact stress to resolve the solution jump that can result in
 238 numerical divergence (Lequesne, 2009; Liaudat et al., 2023) :

$$\sigma'_n = \sigma_n + p_w^m + \sigma_v \quad \text{with} \quad \sigma_v = \zeta \frac{\partial r_n}{\partial t} \quad (27)$$

239 where ζ [Pa · s/m] is the viscosity added to resolve large fast changes in the solution, which occur faster than
 240 the time discretisation, and can cause numerical divergence. The added viscosity ζ slows down the strain rate
 241 and thus stabilised the solution. Detailed discussion on the solution jumps and how the added viscosity helps
 242 mitigate this issue can be found in other works (Lequesne, 2009; Liaudat et al., 2023).

243 2.3.3. Thermal problem

244 The conservation of energy, in terms of temperature, applied to a differential volume of discontinuity $w dl$ reads:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (w \rho_w c_{pw} T^m) + \frac{\partial q_T^l}{\partial l} - q_T^b - q_T^t = 0 \quad (28)$$

245 where q_T^s [J/(m² · s)] is the rate of change of the heat stored in the discontinuity, q_T^l [J/(m · s)] is the longitudinal
 246 heat flow, q_T^b [J/(m² · s)] and q_T^t [J/(m² · s)] are the normal heat flows incoming from the surrounding continuum
 247 medium via bottom and top faces to the discontinuity, respectively.

248 The terms in Eq. (28) can be expanded as:

$$q_T^l = -w \lambda_w \frac{\partial T^m}{\partial l} + c_{pw} q_w^l T^m \quad (29)$$

$$q_{\Gamma}^b = -\lambda_w \frac{2\check{T}^b}{\max(w, \bar{w})} + c_{pw} q_w^b \check{T}^b \quad (30)$$

$$q_{\Gamma}^t = -\lambda_w \frac{2\check{T}^t}{\max(w, \bar{w})} + c_{pw} q_w^t \check{T}^t \quad (31)$$

249 where $\check{T}^b = T^m - T^b$ and $\check{T}^t = T^m - T^t$ are the temperature jumps between the bottom or top face and the
 250 mid-plane, with T^m , T^b and T^t being the temperatures at the mid-plane, bottom and top face of interface
 251 element, respectively, and λ_w is the thermal conductivity of the water. \bar{w} is a penalty coefficient to avoid
 252 singularity when interface elements are used to provide potential cracking paths in intact rock. The penalty
 253 coefficient should be as small as possible to reduce the artificial compliance.

254 3. Validation against cyclic Brazilian tests

255 The formulation and numerical implementation (without fatigue) has been previous verified for thermo-hydraulic
 256 behaviour (using Lauwerier's problem) and for hydro-mechanical problem (the KGD model) for the combined
 257 continuum element and interface elements approach (Luo et al., 2025). In addition, a verification between using
 258 only continuum elements and the combined continuum / interface elements approach for intact material, i.e.
 259 prior to fracturing occurring, was successful when the interfaces were given a high stiffness. In this section, the
 260 proposed method is validated against cyclic Brazilian tests conducted by Erarslan and Williams (2012).

261 3.1. Description of the experiment

262 The Brazilian test, also known as the splitting tensile strength test, is a common method to estimate the tensile
 263 strength of brittle rocks. In this test, a circular disc is placed between loading platens or curved loading jaws,
 264 and diametrically loaded until failure (Fig. 4a). Upon loading, a line of equally-distributed tensile stress is
 265 induced in the centre of the specimen, as shown in Fig. 4b. The compressive force applied at failure (defined
 266 as the maximum force that the sample can sustain) F_{\max} [N] is used to calculate the tensile strength σ_{n0} [Pa]
 267 according to:

$$\sigma_{n0} = -\frac{2F_{\max}}{\pi dh\alpha} \left(\sin\alpha - \frac{\alpha}{2} \right) \quad (32)$$

268 where d [m] and h [m] are the radius and the thickness of the disc, respectively, and α is the contact angle
 269 between the disc and the curved loading jaw (Navidtehrani et al., 2022).

270 In the work of Erarslan and Williams (2012), Brisbane tuff was used to produce specimens with a diameter of
 271 52 mm and a thickness of 26 mm. The material properties are presented in Tab. 1. The tensile strength was
 272 obtained using Equation (32) based on monotonic Brazilian tests. The shear strength is not reported in the
 273 original paper (Erarslan and Williams, 2012), but is set high in the following simulations to avoid numerical
 274 difficulties resulting from the strong stress concentration at the contact arc. The specimens were used to
 275 conduct monotonic and cyclic Brazilian tests in a setup, whose two jaws were designed to make contact with
 276 the specimen at diametrically opposed surfaces over an arc of contact of $\alpha = 10^\circ$ (Erarslan and Williams, 2012).
 277 The specimens were loaded with monotonic or cyclic loading at a rate of 200 N/s. In the monotonic loading
 278 case (in this paper sample BR-3 is taken as an example), the sample failed when the loading reached 20.98
 279 kN. This case will be simulated first to explore the mesh sensitivity. A series of cyclic Brazilian tests with
 280 constant amplitude at 95%, 90%, 80% and 70% of F_{\max} (the load at failure under monotonic loading) were

281 performed to determine the fatigue life, with the experimental S-N relation and fitted relationship presented
 282 in Fig. 5. The cases of cyclic tests with constant amplitude at 95% and 90% of F_{\max} are then simulated to
 283 validate the modelling approach against experimental results, with a special focus on the experimental fatigue
 284 life and fracture patterns.

Table 1: Material properties and model parameters (Erarslan and Williams, 2012).

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Material properties			
Young's modulus	E	2.6E10	Pa
Poisson's ratio	ν	0.26	-
Mode-I fracture stiffness	K_{IC}	1.18E6	Pa · m ^{0.5}
Tensile strength (BR-3, used for monotonic loading)	σ_{n0}	9.87E6	Pa
Tensile strength (used for cyclic loading)	σ_{n0}	10.82E6	Pa
Shear strength	σ_{l0}	400E6	Pa
Model parameters			
Cracking separation	r_{n0}/r_{l0}	1E-7/1E-6	m
Debonding separation	r_{nc}/r_{lc}	1E-5/1E-4	m
Stiffness of interface elements	K_{n0}	9.87E13 or 10.82E13	Pa
Mechanical viscosity	ζ	1E9	Pa · s/m
Parameter a in Eq. (26)	a	-0.051085	-
Parameter b in Eq. (26)	b	0.9929	-

Fig. 4: (a) Description of Brazilian test; (b) description of the numerical model, depicting tensile stress distribution along the centre of the disc. Note the interface elements are inserted in-between all the continuum elements to provide arbitrary potential cracking paths.

Fig. 5: Experiment and simulation results of fatigue life M_f under different maximum loading σ_A . Experimental data is from Erarslan and Williams (2012).

3.2. Numerical model

A 2D model is constructed to simulate the monotonic and cyclic Brazilian tests (Fig. 4b). The bottom arc with a contact angle of 10° is fixed in both x and y directions, while a distributed monotonic or cyclic load is applied at the top arc. The domain is meshed with second-order triangular elements, and interface elements are inserted between all triangular elements to allow fractures to develop in arbitrary directions. Three different meshes are constructed to investigate mesh sensitivity of the model, as shown in Fig. 6a to 6c. Fig. 6a presents a coarse mesh (mesh A, 1770 continuum elements) with a straight line imposed along the central axis of the circle, since a straight fracture is predicted to be induced along the central axis according to analytical solutions (International Society for Rock Mechanics, 1978; Navidtehrani et al., 2022). Interface elements were inserted between all continuum elements. Yet, due to the likely highest tension values along this straight line, it provides a preferential cracking path. In contrast, Fig. 6b and 6c present a coarse (mesh B, 1484 continuum elements) and a finer mesh (mesh C, 12268 continuum elements), respectively, without the imposed straight line along the central axis, and interface elements inserted between all continuum elements. Consequently, no cracking path along the central axis is prescribed in the meshes of Fig. 6b and 6c. The model parameters are shown in Tab. 1. The tensile strength and the debonding separation are determined from material tensile strength and mode-I fracture stiffness. The stiffness of the interface element is set to a high value to reduce artificial compliance while managing numerical convergence.

Fig. 6: Mesh sensitivity analysis. (a) - (c): three different meshes consisting of second-order triangle continuum elements and interface elements that are inserted between all the continuum elements to provide arbitrary potential cracking paths. (a) Coarse mesh (1770 continuum elements) with a straight line imposed along the central axis of the circle; (b) coarse mesh (1484 continuum elements) without the imposed straight line along the central axis; (c) finer mesh (12268 continuum elements) without the imposed straight line along the central axis. (d) - (f): Corresponding simulated damage variable under an axial load of 20.98 kN, indicating the fracture patterns. (g) - (i): Distribution of σ_x at failure.

3.3. Numerical simulation of the monotonic Brazilian test

Simulation results of the monotonic Brazilian test on sample BR-3 are discussed here. The loading was applied at a rate of 200 N/S until a maximum load of 20.98 kN was reached, consistent with the experiment. A sensitivity analysis of the mesh is first conducted, with the results shown in Fig. 6d to 6i. In Fig. 6d to 6f, the damage variable D is shown to highlight the simulated fracture patterns at failure for the three meshes. Fig. 6d shows that a straight fracture along the central axis is simulated with mesh A, in which a straight

308 line (of interface elements) is imposed along the central axis. This is consistent with the experimental fracture
309 pattern shown in Fig. 7b and the theoretical solution. The loading at failure is 20.98 kN, which corresponds
310 to a tensile strength of 9.87 MPa, showing good agreement with the input tensile strength. Fig. 6g presents
311 the corresponding horizontal stress at failure, having a maximum tension of around 7.25 MPa, indicating a
312 relaxation of stress after the tensile fracture occurs.

313 In contrast, no damage is seen in Fig. 6e with mesh B, in which the mesh is coarse and no straight line is
314 imposed along the central axis, and consequently the interface elements in the centre do not orient vertically. In
315 Fig. 6h tension of approximately 10 MPa (exceeding the tensile strength) appears along the central axis, thus
316 should induce fractures, but does not due to the mesh orientation. Instead, the fracture can only be induced if
317 the load is increased to 29.12 kN in the simulation using the coarse mesh in Fig. 6b, almost 40% higher than the
318 20.98 kN in the experiment. This is because the interface elements in the centre are orientated approximately
319 30° away from the vertical. Consequently, the tensile stresses on these non-vertical interface elements are less
320 than the maximum tensile stress, which is in the horizontal direction. Although mesh B cannot accurately
321 predict the applied failure loading, it does accurately represent the stress distribution, which allows the mesh
322 to be adjusted for a follow-up analysis. This highlights the impact of allowing fractures which conform only to
323 element edges, illustrating that an iterative simulation approach may be needed to obtain an accurate outcome.
324 Alternatively, if the mesh in the central part of the model is made sufficiently fine (to automatically generate
325 some straight mesh edges in the central part), as in the mesh C shown in Fig. 6c, the central fracture can
326 be simulated (Fig. 6f), even though the fracture still has to follow the element edges. In Fig. 6i, σ_x is
327 again relaxed along the central axis with a distribution similar to that of Fig. 6g as a result of fracture(s)
328 formation. Due to the less structured alignment of the mesh, the fracture distribution is less even and leads to
329 a less even stress distribution immediately around the fracture zone, resulting in a calculated tensile strength
330 of 8.85 MPa. The mesh sensitivity analysis highlights the influence of the mesh orientation and mesh density
331 on the simulation results, although the stresses prior to fracturing are almost identical. A priori knowledge
332 of the position and direction of the maximum tensile stress is therefore helpful when using of coarse mesh,
333 underscoring the importance of the analytical solutions. Otherwise, several different meshes may be used to
334 capture the correct fracture propagation.

335 Based on the model with mesh presented in Fig. 6a, a comparison of simulated and experimental axial and
336 lateral strains is presented in Fig. 7a, showing generally good agreement with a slight deviation, associated
337 with the artificial compliance resulting from insertion of interface elements. In addition, failure can be clearly
338 seen at the turning point on the simulated curve when loading reaches 20.98 kN, as shown in Fig. 7a, indicating
339 increasing strain since the specimen failed and could not sustain the controlled loading. The peak loading is
340 reached at time step 104.9 s.

Fig. 7: (a) Comparison of experimental and numerical results of axial and lateral strain in the monotonic Brazilian test on sample BR-3. (b) Sample BR-3 after failure under monotonic loading in the experiment ¹.

3.4. Numerical simulation of the cyclic Brazilian test

A series of cyclic experimental tests with maximum loading at 95%, 90%, 80% and 70% of F_{\max} (23 kN) was performed to determine the corresponding fatigue life (Erarslan and Williams, 2012). In this section, the numerical model with the mesh imposed with a straight line along the central axis (Fig. 6a) is used to simulate the cyclic Brazilian tests. Based on the element test data shown in Fig. 5, both parameters a and b of the empirical relationship (Eq. 26) can be determined. In addition, the tensile strength is chosen as 10.87 MPa, as derived from the maximum force applied F_{\max} (23 kN). Other material properties and model parameters are kept the same as shown in Tab. 1. We select the cases where the maximum loading during cyclic loading are 95% and 90% of F_{\max} (23kN) as examples to demonstrate the capability of the proposed model.

Figs. 8a and 8c show the lateral and axial strain evolution with time. It is clearly shown that a sudden sharp increase in lateral strain is observed in the 8th and 54th cycles in the cases of 95% and 90% $\sigma_{\max 0}$, respectively. As is shown in Fig. 5, the predicted fatigue life is captured by the S-N curve fitted from the experimental data. In addition, as opposed to the single failure observed in monotonic tests, a complex fracture pattern is seen in the experimental results, resulting in an overall failure of the sample (Fig. 9), with the numerical results also indicating a network of fractures. The predicted fatigue life and fracture patterns consistent with the experimental results thereby demonstrate the capability of the proposed method to capture the fatigue damage due to cyclic loading at different loading amplitudes.

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Fig. 8: Lateral (positive) and axial (negative) strain evolution with time and loading under different cyclic loadings.

(a) Failed sample under cyclic loading in the experiment. ²

(b) Failed sample under cyclic loading in the simulation.

Fig. 9: Comparison of the failed sample under cyclic loading in the experiment and in the simulation (95% $\sigma_{\max 0}$).

358 To further demonstrate the capability of the proposed model to handle varying-amplitude cyclic loading, two

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359 synthetic loading cases (not performed experimentally) with varying-amplitude cyclic loading are simulated. In
 360 Case A, the applied maximum load is equal to 90% $\sigma_{\max 0}$ for the first 10 cycles, before increasing to to 95%
 361 $\sigma_{\max 0}$ in the later cycles (Fig. 10a). The corresponding results (Fig. 10b) show that failure of the sample
 362 happens at the 15th cycle, less than the fatigue life (54 cycles) under cyclic loading with constant maximum
 363 loading at 90% $\sigma_{\max 0}$ but more than that (8 cycles) under cyclic loading with constant maximum loading at
 364 95% $\sigma_{\max 0}$. Inspired by the results from Case A, the applied maximum load in Case B is set to 95% $\sigma_{\max 0}$
 365 in the first 5 cycles, before decreasing to 90% $\sigma_{\max 0}$ in later cycles (Fig. 10c). Interestingly, unlike Case A
 366 where failure happens after 14 cycles (first 10 lower-amplitude cyclic loading + later 4 higher-amplitude cyclic
 367 loading), failure is seen in the 31st cycle in Case B (Fig. 10d).

(a) Applied varying-amplitude cyclic loading in case A.

(b) Strain evolution in case A.

(c) Applied varying-amplitude cyclic loading in case B.

(d) Strain evolution in case B.

Fig. 10: Simulation results of varying-amplitude cyclic loading and corresponding lateral and axial strain evolution cases.

368 4. Validation against cyclic hydraulic fracturing test

369 4.1. Description of the experiment

370 The hydraulic fracturing test is widely used to determine the tensile strength of rocks and/or the magnitude
 371 of the in situ stresses. Zhuang et al. (2019) conducted laboratory (cyclic) hydraulic fracturing tests on granite
 372 samples cored from the Pocheon geothermal field to demonstrate the concept of cyclic stimulation. The targeted
 373 Pocheon granite contained three orthogonal cleavage planes, namely the rift (R), graine (G) and hardway (H)
 374 planes. Specimens used in the experiments were cored perpendicular to each of the R, G and H planes, and

375 thus are labelled as R, G and H groups, respectively. The rift plane was seen to have the weakest strength,
 376 with an average measured Brazilian tensile strength equal to 6.1 MPa. Hydraulic fracturing tests on specimens
 377 in Group G and H were seen to induce fractures in the weakest rift plane. In this paper, we focus only on the
 378 fracturing tests on specimens from group H, with the orientation of the sample and the cleavage planes shown
 379 in Fig. 11a. Other properties of the specimens in group H are presented in Tab. 2.

Fig. 11: Description of the Pocheon granite specimen in group H and the corresponding numerical model. A line of interface elements is used in the model to represent the weakest rift plane, on which fracture can be induced by injection of fluid.

Table 2: Properties of the Pocheon granite specimens in group H and model parameters.

Material properties			
Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Young's modulus	E	5.8E10	Pa
Poisson's ratio	ν	0.30	-
Density	ρ_s	3000	kg/m ³
Tensile strength (rift plane)	σ_{n0}	6.1E6	Pa
Shear strength (rift plane)	σ_{t0}	192E6	Pa
Model parameters			
Cracking separation	r_{n0}/r_{t0}	1E-7/1E-6	m
Debonding separation	r_{nc}/r_{lc}	2E-7/1E-4	m
Mechanical viscosity	ζ	1E12	Pa·s/m
Parameter a in Eq. 26	a	-0.021129	-
Parameter b in Eq. 26	b	0.90437	-

380 A borehole with a diameter of 8 mm was drilled through the central axis of the specimens to allow the injection
 381 of fluid, as is shown in Fig. 11a. Two sets of tests were conducted, one using a controlled pressurisation rate
 382 and the other with a controlled injection rate. Here, we focus on the tests of controlled injection rate (100
 383 mm³/s), in which the horizontal confining pressure is zero while the vertical stress was 25 MPa to prevent fluid
 384 leakage from the top and bottom surfaces. Monotonic fracturing was first implemented using 12 specimens to
 385 determine an average monotonic breakdown pressure, which was 6.9 MPa. Cyclic fracturing tests then followed
 386 with a maximum injection pressure ranging from 74% to 95% of the monotonic breakdown pressure, using

387 another 34 samples. Since injection rate was controlled, the injection time was therefore adjusted to achieve the
 388 desired injection pressure. Fig. 12 presents the number of cycles needed to fail the specimens under different
 389 maximum injection pressure in the experiments. Despite the noticeable scatter in the experimental data, a linear
 390 regression in the \log_{10} basis is applied, since this formulation adequately represents the pronounced reduction
 391 in strength during the early loading cycles and the fatigue limit identified experimentally (Cerfontaine and
 392 Collin, 2018). The fitting function results in a standard deviation of 0.043, indicating the function captures
 393 the trend generally well. The noticeable scatter in the experimental data reflects the inherent heterogeneity
 394 of rock strength and microstructure. The present cohesive zone model employs uniform material parameters
 395 and therefore represents an average material response. As such, local variability in strength or stiffness is not
 396 explicitly modelled. Incorporating spatially variable or stochastic parameters could further improve the ability
 397 of the model to capture experimental scatter and is a next step to be taken.

Fig. 12: Experiment and simulation results of fatigue life M_f under different maximum injection pressure p_{inj} .

398 4.2. Numerical model

399 A 2D model is constructed to simulate both the monotonic and cyclic fracturing tests (Fig. 11b). Only half of
 400 the horizontal section of the specimen is considered due to symmetric condition. A line of interface elements is
 401 inserted along the symmetry axis to represent the weakest rift plane, along which fracture can be induced upon
 402 fluid injection. The solid elements represent the rock matrix, which is assumed to be impermeable due to its
 403 extremely low permeability. The bottom boundaries of the model are fixed along the y direction, with two nodes
 404 at the left and right sides fixed along the x direction to provide reaction to the whole system. No confining stress
 405 is applied matching the experimental conditions. Other model input parameters for the interface elements are
 406 summarised in Tab. 2.

407 4.3. Numerical simulation of the monotonic injection tests

408 Monotonic fracturing is first simulated to demonstrate the capability of the model and determine the simulated
 409 monotonic breakdown pressure. A ramped injection rate, shown in Fig. 13a, is used to simulate the borehole

410 storage effect. Fig. 13 compares the simulation and experimental results of the monotonic hydraulic fracturing
 411 test. It shows that the numerical model can successfully capture the pressure response with a peak pressure at
 412 6.48 MPa (compared to 6.9 MPa in the experiment). Additionally, the damage variable of the all of the interface
 413 elements is recorded in the simulation and averaged and compared with the AE records of the experiment. Both
 414 values represent the damage process of the rock sample in different ways. When the averaged damage variable
 415 reaches 1, it indicates the whole line of interface elements is fully opened. The time period over which the
 416 damage variable increases from zero to 1 is the same time period with the AE events with the highest amplitude
 417 and most densely recorded events.

Fig. 13: Comparison of experiment and simulation results of pressure response and damage evolution during monotonic hydraulic fracturing test.

4.4. Simulation results of the cyclic injection tests

419 The model then is used to simulate the cyclic fracturing tests to validate against the experimental fatigue life,
 420 with the maximum injection pressure reaching 90%, 87% and 85% of the simulated p_b^{ave} (6.48 MPa) in each
 421 cycle. Each cycle has the same injection rate and time period, so in cases where damage (partially) occurs, the
 422 achieved pressure is lower than the initial pressure. The same domain and input parameters are used as in the
 423 monotonic simulations.

424 The simulated pressure response and averaged damage variable under different cyclic injection pressure are
 425 presented in Fig. 14. Fig. 14 shows the granite sample fails in the 2nd cycle, 63rd cycle and 231st cycle under
 426 a cyclic injection pressure of 90% p_b^{mono} , 87% p_b^{mono} and 85% p_b^{mono} respectively. The relationship between the
 427 fatigue life and the cyclic injection pressure is plotted as blue rectangles in Fig. 12, showing a good agreement
 428 with the S-N curve fitted from experimental data. Therefore, the proposed model can successfully reproduce
 429 the fatigue damage due to cyclic hydraulic stimulation. It should be noted that the domain simulated with the
 430 model cannot reproduce the fracture branches observed during the cyclic stimulation experiments, as shown in
 431 Fig. 15b. This is because a single line of zero-thickness interface elements is used to represent the failure plane,
 432 while the failure plane(s) in real rock may be more heterogeneous driven by small scale heterogeneities. However,
 433 since the fracture branches will most likely be restricted within a similar zone due to geometric conditions, a single
 434 line of interface elements along this weak plane is reasonably able to capture the main fracture. To be able to
 435 simulate the fracture branches, interface elements would need to be inserted in-between all continuum elements
 436 with mesh fine enough to capture the pattern, as is done in the simulation of the cyclic Brazilian test.

(a) Pressure response under $p_{inj} = 90\%p_b^{mono}$.

(b) Pressure response under $p_{inj} = 87\%p_b^{mono}$.

(c) Pressure response under $p_{inj} = 85\%p_b^{mono}$.

Fig. 14: Simulated pressure response and evolution of the average damage variable under different p_{inj} .

Fig. 15: Comparison of fracture pattern in experiments and simulation. (a) Observed fracture pattern in the monotonic stimulation experiment; (b) Observed fracture pattern in the cyclic stimulation (after 65 cycles) experiment; (c) Simulated fracture pattern in the cyclic stimulation (after 63 cycles with the maximum injection pressure reaching 87% of the p_b^{ave}). Subfigures (a) and (b) are from Zhuang et al. (2019) with copyright license ³.

437 Viscous stress is added in Eq. 27 to resolve large fast changes in the solution, which occur faster than the time
438 discretisation, and can cause numerical divergence. The added viscosity ζ slows down the strain rate and thus
439 stabilised the solution, however it could also have an impact on the predicted behaviour including the fatigue
440 life. To investigate the impact of the added viscosity, simulations of the cyclic hydraulic fracturing test are run
441 with four different viscosities, i.e., $\zeta = 0$ Pa·s/m, $1E11$ Pa·s/m, $1E12$ Pa·s/m and $1E13$ Pa·s/m. The predicted
442 fatigue life for different injection pressures with the different viscosities is presented in Fig. 12. It is seen that
443 by increasing the viscosity, the fatigue life also increases. Here, the impact of the viscosity on the results are
444 discussed in detail for the case under $p_{inj} = 90\% p_b^{mono}$. The simulated injection pressures are shown in Fig. 16.
445 When adding a mechanical viscosity between 0 and $\zeta = 1E12$ Pa·s/m fracturing occurs in the second cycle and at
446 pressure values of within 1 % of each other. However, when the mechanical viscosity is 0 Pa·s/m, the simulation
447 cannot converge when interface elements reach the cracking separation r_{n0} . If a $1E11$ Pa·s/m viscosity is added,
448 the divergence problem reduces slightly, but the simulation still diverges after 1.5 cycles. If more viscosity is
449 added, i.e. $\zeta = 1E12$ Pa·s/m or $1E13$ Pa·s/m, the simulation is able to run continuously, with fatigue life
450 matching the point when the other simulations diverge. However, when adding a larger viscosity, in this case
451 $\zeta = 1E13$ Pa·s/m, damage occurs gradually and increases per cycle, with the fatigue life being significantly
452 increased, see Fig. 12. With a further reduction in injection pressure, the differences become larger, however,
453 these are still in fitting with the experimental behaviour and are therefore considered to be reasonable. The
454 value of viscosity which needs to be added is a function of system stiffness and the element size, and therefore

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Table 3: Properties of the granite samples and parameters used for the interface elements (Hong et al., 2023).

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Properties of the granite samples			
Density	ρ_s	2630	kg/m ³
Young's modulus	E	39.41	GPa
Poisson's ratio	ν	0.28	-
Tensile strength	σ_{n0}	10.02	MPa
Shear strength	σ_{t0}	122	MPa
Permeability	k	1.1E-3	mD
Porosity	ϕ	0.0045	-
Linear thermal expansion coefficient*	α	4.8E-6	K ⁻¹
Thermal conductivity	λ	3.1	W/(m · K)
Parameters of the interface elements			
Cracking separation	r_{n0}/r_{t0}	1E-8/1E-6	m
Debonding separation	r_{nc}/r_{tc}	1E-5/1E-4	m
Mechanical viscosity	ζ	1E12	Pa·s/m
Parameter a in Eq. 26	a	-1.0	-
Parameter b in Eq. 26	b	0.99	-

Fig. 17: Description of the granite samples used in the experiment and the corresponding 2D numerical model. A line of interface elements is used in the model to represent the potential fracture path, on which fracture can be induced by injection of fluid.

470 The experiments consisted of two phases: (1) cooling-heating cycles; (2) fracturing test via injection of cold

^{3*}: The thermal expansion coefficient is calculated from the thermal expansion coefficient of the dominant minerals' (30% K-feldspar and 47% oligoclase). Data from Hong et al. (2023).

471 water. Fig. 18 shows the evolution of the borehole temperature and injection pressure during one single cooling-
 472 heating cycle and during the fracturing test respectively. The samples were firstly pre-heated to 473 K in a
 473 muffle furnace. Then, the samples were loaded with initial stresses of $\sigma_v = 15$ MPa, $\sigma_H = 10$ MPa and $\sigma_h = 7$
 474 MPa in a true triaxial fracturing equipment (Hong et al., 2023), which is designed to insulate the sample and
 475 allows the injection of fluid. In both phases, a 600-second natural cooling down of the samples happened first
 476 before any injection of cold water (Stage I in Figs. 18a and 18b).

477 In the cooling-heating cycle, shown in Fig. 18a, water with temperature of 323 K was injected into the borehole
 478 with a constant low injection pressure of 2 MPa, lasting for 180 seconds (Stage II in Fig. 18a). After injection
 479 stopped, the open hole naturally re-heated and then cooled (Stage III in Fig. 18a). The samples were then
 480 removed from the triaxial equipment and re-heated to 473 K in the muffle furnace (Stage IV in Fig. 18a) before
 481 the next cooling-heating cycle. After the required cooling-heating cycles, the samples were then subjected to
 482 high-pressure injection of cold water to determine the (reduced) breakdown pressure, shown in Fig. 18b. In
 483 contrast to the cooling-heating cycle, water with temperature of 323 K was injected into the borehole with
 484 a constant injection rate of $30 \text{ mm}^3/\text{min}$, leading to an average pressurisation rate of 0.386 MPa/s until the
 485 breakdown pressure. Four cases were performed by Hong et al. (2023), including monotonic fracturing test
 486 without cooling-heating cycle, 1 cycles, 3 cycles and 5 cycles of such cooling and heating, which were labelled as
 487 W7, W8, W2 and W9 respectively (Hong et al., 2023). Experimental results show that a decreased breakdown
 488 pressure was observed with the number of cooling-heating cycles increasing, as presented in Fig. 19.

Fig. 18: Changes of borehole temperature and injection pressure in (a) one single cooling-heating cycle; and (b) monotonic fracturing test.

Fig. 19: Breakdown pressure in the fracturing tests against the number of cooling-heating cycles and simulations (Hong et al., 2023).

489 5.2. Numerical model

490 A 2D symmetric model, shown in Fig. 17b, is constructed. Since a single fracture wing was observed in the
491 direction of σ_H after fracturing tests in the experiments, only a single line of interface elements are inserted the
492 direction of σ_H in the model to represent the potential fracture path, which also aids to reduce the computational
493 burden. Initial stresses of $\sigma_H = 10$ MPa and $\sigma_h = 7$ MPa are applied. The continuum elements are set to be
494 impermeable due to the extremely low permeability of the granite, but heat conduction is allowed. Water
495 is injected into the interface elements from the mid-node of the interface element at the borehole wall. In
496 Stage II of the cooling-heating cycles, the injection pressure is kept constant at 2 MPa. In contrast, during
497 the fracturing stage, the injection rate is ramped to 30 mm³/min in 60 seconds and then kept constant. This
498 simulated the storage effect, where in the experiment the pressure build-up rate was an average of 0.386 MPa/s.
499 The temperature at the borehole is controlled based on its evolution shown in Fig. 18.

500 The key parameters for the interface element are presented in the Tab. 3. Tensile strength was determined
501 via Brazilian test in original paper (Hong et al., 2023). The stiffness is set to a high value to reduce artificial
502 compliance, while the de-bonding separation is estimated from granite toughness. The artificial mechanical
503 viscosity was chosen to be 1E12Pa · s/m based on the sensitivity analysis in Section 4.4 and the similarity in
504 material properties and element size. Since no element tests are available for the samples used in this experiment,
505 the S-N relationship is determined based on the results of the breakdown pressure, shown in Fig. 19. However,
506 since this is a fully THM coupled problem, the actual applied normal stress (σ_A) on the first interface element
507 at the borehole during cooling-heating cycles and the degraded tensile strength (σ_{nm}) after cycles cannot be
508 obtained directly. First, to determine σ_A in the Equation 26, a coupled THM simulation of the cooling stage
509 is performed to determine the largest tangential stress $\sigma_t^{\text{cooling}}$ (at the wellbore in the direction of σ_H) reached
510 during cooling, which is σ_A . To determine the degraded tensile strength σ_{nm} , a coupled THM simulation of
511 the fracturing stage with high-pressure injection is performed to determine the tangential stress σ_t^{frac} (at the

512 wellbore in the direction of σ_H). We simulate the monotonic fracturing test, and pick the tangential stresses
513 σ_t^{frac} at which the normalised injection pressure (defined as the ratio of the injection pressure to the monotonic
514 breakdown pressure, p/p_b^{mono}) reaches the corresponding normalised breakdown pressures (p_b/p_b^{mono}) under
515 different cycles in the experiments. These picked tangential stresses σ_t^{frac} are viewed as the degraded tensile
516 strengths σ_{nm} after different cooling cycles, as is shown in Tab. 4.

517 Now we have three data points of different cycles with corresponding degraded tensile strengths under a given
518 normal stress σ_A (σ_A here is constant since in stage 1 the injection pressure and temperature were not changed.)
519 Based on the expression of σ_{nm} ($= (1 - D_f)\sigma_{n0}$), 24 and 26, we can determine the corresponding fatigue life M_f
520 of these three cases. Then the parameter a and b can be obtained by best-fitting the three data points.

Table 4: Degraded tensile strengths from the the experimental data (obtained by simulating the fracturing test under monotonic injection) and from the simulation considering fatigue damage.

No. of cycles	Exp. p_b/p_b^{mono} , MPa	Exp. σ_{nm}/σ_{n0} , MPa	Simu. D_f	Simu. σ_{nm}/σ_{n0} , MPa
0	1	1	0	1
1	0.94	0.95	0.228	0.77
3	0.80	0.68	0.452	0.55
5	0.55	0.17	0.675	0.33

521 5.3. Results and discussion

522 Fig. 20a presents the normalised injection pressure response during the monotonic fracturing test (i.e. without
523 a cooling-heating cycle) while Fig. 19 compares the exact injection pressure during monotonic fracturing in
524 the experiment and simulation. The simulated monotonic breakdown pressure p_b is 19.5 MPa, around 20 %
525 lower than that (24.7 MPa) observed in the experiment. The working hypothesis is that the tensile strength
526 used in the model was taken from the strength measured at room temperature via the Brazilian test (Hong
527 et al., 2023), while the sample was heated to 473 K before conducting the fracturing test. Other possible
528 factors include the chosen values of the linear thermal expansion coefficient α and the thermal conductivity λ .
529 In the simulation, α is estimated based on the thermal expansion coefficients of the dominant minerals (30%
530 K-feldspar and 47% oligoclase) of the granite used in the experiment (Hong et al., 2023). However, the overall
531 linear thermal expansion coefficient of the rock sample could be different from the one calculated from mineral
532 components. In addition, the thermal conductivity is not mentioned in their paper, and is estimated here.
533 Moreover, due to the limited number of samples tested, sample heterogeneity could play a significant role.

534 Figs. 20b, 20c and 20d shows the normalised pressure response during the fracturing tests after 1, 3 and 5
535 cooling-heating cycles, respectively. A clear trend of decreasing p_b with increasing number of cycles that was
536 observed in the experiment is well reproduced in the simulation, as is demonstrated in also Fig. 19. The
537 decreased p_b is a result of the fatigue damage accumulated during the cooling-heating cycles, in which both
538 the thermal stress and the 2 MPa injection pressure have an impact. The accumulated fatigue damage and
539 corresponding simulated σ_{nm}/σ_{n0} are listed in Tab. 4. The fatigue damage variable D_f increases with increasing
540 number of cooling cycles, contributing to the reduced breakdown pressure. One thing worth explaining is that
541 the values of σ_{nm}/σ_{n0} after 1 and 3 cycles are lower than their counterparts determined from experimental data,
542 while the value after 5 cycles is higher. This is because the S-N curve is determined by best-fitting for the three
543 data points, leading to an overall least distance to these three points while different differences between the
544 simulated and experimental σ_{nm}/σ_{n0} .

Fig. 20: Normalised pressure (p_b/p_b^{mono}) response during the fracturing tests of the selected cases W7 (monotonic injection without cooling-heating cycle), W8 (1 cycle), W2 (3 cycles) and W9 (5 cycles) in the experiment and simulation. Note that the simulation is stopped after the breakdown pressure is overcome.

545 6. Conclusions

546 A new cohesive zone model has been developed to simulate rock fatigue failure under cyclic coupled thermo-
 547 hydro-mechanical loading. The model incorporates a fatigue damage variable into the elasto-damage constitutive
 548 law that governs the mechanical response of the interface element, which can represent both pre-existing and
 549 newly formed fractures. The fatigue damage variable evolves according to the number and magnitude of the
 550 cycles, allowing the tensile strength and stiffness of the interface element to progressively degrade. Palmgren-
 551 Miner's rule is further integrated to account for varying-amplitude cyclic loading.

552 The proposed method is validated against three laboratory experiments from the literature that involve differ-
 553 ent thermo-hydro-mechanical coupling: a cyclic Brazilian test, a cyclic hydraulic fracturing test, and a cyclic
 554 thermal stimulation test. In all cases, the model successfully reproduces the observed fatigue damage or the re-
 555 duction in breakdown pressure associated with cyclic injection or cyclic thermal treatments. A mesh sensitivity
 556 analysis indicates that the mesh orientation and density can impact the fracture pattern and simulated rock
 557 mass strength. Results improve when stress distributions are known a priori, for example through analytical

558 solutions or by using different meshes. The ability of the method to handle varying-amplitude cyclic loading
559 is demonstrated by the simulation of a synthetic cyclic loading based on the Brazilian test, which shows that
560 fatigue life is shorter when low-amplitude cycles precede high-amplitude cycles than in the opposite loading
561 order. Moreover, a sensitivity analysis of the mechanical viscosity, which is added to slow down the strain
562 rate and thus stabilise the numerical solution, shows that increasing the mechanical viscosity can lead to an
563 increasing fatigue life.

564 The three validation tests confirm the validity of the proposed method to capture the fatigue damage arising
565 from cyclic mechanical, hydro-mechanical, or thermo-hydro-mechanical processes, including cases with varying
566 amplitude. The method can therefore be used to support the design of cyclic thermal stimulation strategy
567 for geo-energy projects, such as geothermal energy production. Extensive experimentation may be needed to
568 determine the fatigue damage variable evolution, and further efforts could be made to determine this more
569 efficiently, e.g. from data collected during field tests.

570 Finally, cyclic fatigue damage is explicitly included in the present model and is governed solely by the number
571 and magnitude of loading cycles. Creep-induced fatigue (i.e. time-dependent failure under constant sub-critical
572 stress) is not captured, making the model most suitable for stiff and brittle rocks in which creep effects are
573 negligible over the timescale of interest. In addition, the fatigue damage variable currently depends on the peak
574 stress of each cycle rather than on the full stress path. This formulation enables practical calibration for stress
575 paths typical of stimulation campaigns but requires dedicated experiments need to establish the S-N relation
576 when substantially different stress paths are involved. Future efforts to generalise the fatigue damage variable,
577 such as expressing it in terms of the cumulative total strain energy, could reduce this dependence on specific
578 loading scenarios and allow a unified representation of fatigue damage across diverse THM conditions.

579 **Author contributions**

580 **Wen Luo:** Conceptualisation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal Analysis, Data Curation, Writing -
581 Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualisation.

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587 Supervision, Project Administration, Funding Acquisition.

588 **Declaration of competing interest**

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